

NFDI4Earth

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Annual USN Improvement Report

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Executive summary

The report consists of three tables listing the quantitative indicators, comments from users regarding the quality and additional steps taken in the process of establishing and improving the user support of the NFDI4Earth community in 2024.

The concept ([D2.2.4](#)) explains the idea of the framework and additional ways of documentation in order to improve the quality of user support by the network.

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1 Improvement indicators

1. Total number of user requests and number per category
2. Efficiency of support
3. User experience and feedback
4. Composition and personal size of the USN
5. Integration and monitoring of the external experts network (Expert HUB)
6. Outreach activities

2 Total number of user requests and number per category

Indicator	2023	2024
1 – Number of opened tickets since last report	13	40
2 – Mean duration of open tickets (days)	-	
3 – User experience and feedback	-	15
4 – Number of USN partners / active agents	8/8	9/10
5 – Number of external experts involved	0	2
6 – Number of LHB articles and other output	3	5

3 Efficiency of support

In 2024, the User Support Network processed a total of 40 tickets via the Znuny system. Since we were still in the setup phase, not all tickets represented actual interactions with users within and outside the community. Of the 23 actual user requests, 16 (approximately 70%) received an initial response within the targeted time frame of 2–5 working days, thereby maintaining the expected baseline responsiveness.

To evaluate the efficiency of the support process, we measured the First Contact Resolution Score (FCRS) – the proportion of tickets resolved entirely by the 1st level support.

In 2024, the FCRS was 48% (11 out of 23 actual user requests were resolved directly by the first level support team). Since 2024 was our first year of operation, we do not have comparative data from 2023. This baseline FCRS will serve as a benchmark for future evaluations.

Znuny metrics were used to evaluate the average ticket processing time and number of interactions per ticket:

- Average processing time: ~56 days*
- Average interactions per ticket: 7.1 (164 total interactions across 23 tickets)
- Min/Max interactions per ticket: 3/16

* This number is influenced by process establishment issues, as some tickets were formally closed long after their actual resolution

To address these challenges and improve our support capabilities, we implemented several key actions during 2024:

Action 5: Increase number of agents

- The support network grew from 10 nominal agents (8 active) at the start of 2023 to 19 nominal agents (10 active) by the end of 2024, representing a 90% increase in support capacity.
- 2 additional queues were established (Coordination & Feedback)

Action 6: Improve knowledge base

- Development of internal documentation and standardized response templates is in progress.

Action 7: Increase external expert network

- A workflow for integrating external experts into support processes has been established.

While significant progress was made in 2024, several areas for improvement were identified based on our operational metrics:

1. Ticket closure process needs further refinement

- The improved process needs to be fully established in daily practice
- Target: Significantly reduce the average processing time from the current 56 days

2. External expert network requires expansion

- Despite establishing an initial workflow, more subject matter experts need to be integrated
- Target: Reduce escalation delays and improve handling of complex technical cases

3. First Contact Resolution Score has potential for growth

- Current baseline of 48% can be increased with better knowledge resources
- Target: Improve FCRS to at least 60% by end of 2025

4. Knowledge base development requires acceleration

- Complete the documentation and response templates currently in progress
- Target: Reduce the average number of interactions needed per ticket

4 Comments on indicators

Date	Quality comments from users
31.12.2024	<p>Generally, there is little feedback from users after they have received an answer via the ticketing system so far.</p> <p>For none of the opened and answered tickets in 2024 did a user report that he/she was not satisfied.</p> <p>For five of the tickets in 2024 users were providing explicitly positive feedback, thanking us for the service provided.</p>

5 Description of improvement steps

Date	Improvement steps taken
31.12.2024	<p>We installed a regular monthly agents meeting to discuss open tickets and unclear workflow procedures (see sec. 6).</p> <p>Close collaboration with NFDI4Earth pilot (2nd cohort) as one-to-one support to promote the service and gain knowledge on missing support topics/categories.</p> <p>The first months of operational work of the NFDI4Earth-Helpdesk indicated the necessity for a scalable solution to include further expert competence into the Helpdesk workflow. A break-out session during the NFDI4Earth plenum was attributed to this topic.</p> <p>A major outcome from the discussion and suggestions during the session was to include experts together with their individual community by connecting them as a kind of Expert-Hub. This approach will allow the contribution of individual experts to the NFDI4Earth Helpdesk but without the necessary official institutional commitment. Ideally, this will ensure the solution- and service-oriented workflow necessary to be a successful product within NFDI4Earth (see sec. 7).</p> <p>Regular contributions to the NFDI4Earth newsletter as "Question of the Quarter" to promote the helpdesk service or highlight "best-practise" examples within the community (see sec. 8).</p> <p>A close collaboration to the network with NFDI helpdesks from connected disciplines (Geo-Chem-Life sciences) was established to easily exchange requests that cover other disciplines and by this improving the helpdesk service.</p>

6 Composition and personal size of the USN

The USN team consists of 9 active agents from various Earth System Science (ESS) research fields (such as Earth science, meteorology, oceanography, hydrology, etc.) and aims to answer user requests from the ESS community on the topic of research data management (RDM) as well as to discuss how to proactively support researchers directly and indirectly with useful RDM

information and guidance. The team's expertise lies in different areas of RDM and covers, e.g., data and its analysis, tools and software, information and metadata, repositories and/or data services. For user inquiries, the field of activity of the individual members includes 1st level or 2nd level support. The USN team meets regularly for discussing the user requests and their handling in the ticket system, for exchange of RDM news as well as for reporting and discussion of the progress with living handbook articles, RDM events, conference activities and activities concerning the collaboration with pilots.

The USN team has recently been expanded by RDM colleagues from the Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research Warnemünde (IOW) who wanted to take the opportunity to participate in the NFDI4Earth network with their extended technical expertise in the field of oceanography, including the FAIR handling of research data and associated infrastructures. In particular, the IOW colleagues can make a reinforcing contribution to the work of the USN team in the areas of oceanographic databases for hydrochemical, biological and meteorological data, data curation, software development, model data server solutions and support for FAIR data processing and publication. Moreover, the IOW RDM team also gains valuable impulses from this collaboration, benefiting from cross-disciplinary perspectives and shared expertise within the broader ESS RDM community.

7 Integration and monitoring of the external experts network (Expert HUB)

The NFDI4Earth user support network consists of a diverse team of Earth data experts. One idea during the time period 2024 was to expand the user support network, to reach more scientific disciplines. Therefore, colleagues were contacted as external experts and listed in a helpdesk list, which can be found as a file document in our SharePoint. The user support network team has now the opportunity to review this document to find external experts to help answer questions where the in-house network does not have the necessary knowledge. Not all external experts (Expert HUB) could be member of the user support team, this must be in one hand of the user support network team, and will be discussed during the monthly user support team meeting.

8 Outreach activities

The NFDI4Earth user support network has been engaged to network and make itself known during the year 2024. We are aware that it is not yet a common behaviour of scientists to look around for help in research data management, but that data managers have to play an active role to get into sight, in order to offer support.

In the first quarter of the year 2024 we started to provide content from our support experience to create user success stories, that can be included into the OneStop4All portal. With these stories we want to give an impression, what kind of solutions are possible and how the RDM support takes place.

We also became visible at workshops and conferences: in April 2024 we were presenting the USN together with other partners of NFDI4Earth at the LURCH workshop (online) and the Data Science Symposium in Bremen. The USN agents also are in a one-to-one relationship assigned to the NFDI4Earth pilot projects. Here we took part in